

A Shiny Web App of the Covering Principle for Multiple Testing

Huajiang Li^a, Bao Nguyen^c, Letong Song^b, Hong Zhou^{c,*}

^a*Xencor, Pasadena, CA 91107, USA*

^b*Montgomery Blair High School, MD 20901, USA*

^c*Arkansas State University, State University, AR 72467, USA*

Abstract

The “covering principle” was recently proposed to address the multiplicity issue in multiple hypotheses testing with a hierarchical structure. In this article, a Shiny web application is developed which makes it convenient for users to build an objective-tailored multiple testing procedure based on the Covering Principle, using any device with a web browser. The Covering Principle is applied to two real clinical trials using the Shiny web application, demonstrating the convenience of the new web application and the flexibility and greater power of the Covering principle relative to the popular gate-keeping method.

Keywords: Closed testing principle, Covering Principle, Dominance relation, Familywise error rate, Gate-keeping, Graphical approach, Multiple testing, Shiny R.

1. Introduction

In modern clinical drug development, it is very common to compare different dose levels on a hierarchical order of endpoints (such as primary, secondary, and tertiary) simultaneously. Therefore, multiple hypotheses would be tested at the same time in a clinical trial. The issue with such multiple hypotheses testing is that the familywise error rate would be inflated even though each test on the individual hypothesis is controlled at the pre-specified significance level. US FDA guidance for Industry (2022) requires that all the multiple testing procedures used in any Phase III trial must strongly control the familywise error rate. In recent decades, Dmitrienko and others have developed a variety of gatekeeping procedures to deal with the clinical trials with multiple hierarchical ordered objectives (Dmitrienko *et al.*, 2003, Dmitrienko *et al.*, 2007; Dmitrienko *et al.*, 2008a, Dmitrienko and Tamhane, 2007; Dmitrienko *et al.*, 2008b,

*Corresponding author

Email address: hzhou@astate.edu; *Phone:* 1-870-972-3090; *Fax:* 1-870-972-3950 (Hong Zhou)

Millen and Dmitrienko 2011; Kordzakhia and Dmitrienko 2013, Dmitrienko and Tamhane ,2011; Dmitrienko and Tamhane ,2013).

Recently, Li and Zhou (2021) introduced the Covering Principle to address the multiplicity issue in multiple hypotheses testing with a hierarchical structure. The Covering Principle uses the dominance relations to describe the hierarchical order among the hypotheses in the sample space, By using dominance relations the Covering Principle decomposes a family of multiple hypotheses into multiple subfamilies of hypotheses to construct a multiple testing procedure.

The purpose of this article is to introduce a Shiny web application for readers to build their own objective-oriented multiple testing procedures using the Covering Principle. With the graphical user interface (GUI) of the Shiny app, users can conduct multiple testing using any device with a web browser, without the need to install R or any specific statistical program.

The article is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly introduces the concept of dominance relations and presents general steps to build multiple testing procedures using the Covering Principle by a motivating example. Section 3 explains the use of the Shiny web application: `CoveringPrincipleMTP`. The detailed aspects for how to construct objective-tailored multiple testing procedures with the Shiny app are illustrated with two clinical trials in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the article with closing remarks.

2. Steps to build multiple testing procedures with the Covering Principle

The following are key steps illustrating how to use the Covering Principle to build a multiple testing procedure.

Step 1. Discuss the development of a test strategy with the medical team, construct the dominance relations among hypotheses, and save them as a `.csv` text file.

Step 2. Decompose the family of null hypotheses into subfamilies by the Shiny web app, which will be illustrated Sections 3 and 4.

Step 3. Test null hypotheses in each subfamily using an existing α -level multiple testing procedure, such as Holm (1979) or the generalized Holm procedure (Li *et al.* ,2017), the fixed sequence (Maurer *et al.* ,1995; Westfall and Krishen ,2001), the fallback procedure (Wiens ,2003; Wiens and Dmitrienko ,2005), a data-driven fallback procedure (Wolf and Zhou ,2021), or the graphical procedure (Bretz *et al.*,2009), etc.

Step 4. Consolidate the test results from all subfamilies to make conclusions on each individual hypothesis as follows:

(4a) If a hypothesis H_i is not dominated, it will be rejected as long as H_i is rejected in all subfamilies in which it is contained. A hypothesis on the primary endpoint is one that is not dominated.

(4b) If a hypothesis H_i is dominated in multiple dominance relations, in order to ultimately reject H_i , not only must H_i be rejected in all subfamilies in which it is contained, but at least one of H_i 's dominant hypotheses must also be rejected.

2.1. A motivating example

Example 1: Suppose that a simple clinical trial studies the efficacy of a new treatment for a disease. The study has one primary endpoint (P), and two secondary endpoints: S_1, S_2 . If the hypothesis (H_1) on the primary endpoint (P) tests significant and it will result an regulatory claim. Then, either one of the hypotheses H_2 on S_1 or H_3 on S_2 could be tested. If either H_1 or H_2 is significant, additional regulatory claim(s) may be applied. The testing order of hypotheses is displayed by a decision flowchart in Figure 1(a).

The Covering Principle is applied to this clinical trial in the following steps.

Step 1. Construct the dominance relation in terms of the coverage relation of rejection regions.

Following the analysis of the decision flowchart, the coverage relation of rejection regions among R_1, R_2 and R_3 is $R_2 \cup R_3 \subseteq R_1$ and can also be visualized by the Venn diagram in Figure 1(b), where R_i is the rejection region of $H_i, i = 1, 2, 3$. If the value of the test statistic from this sample data falls in the rejection region R_2 , then H_2 is rejected. Since $R_2 \cup R_3 \subseteq R_1$, consequently, H_1 must be already rejected. Please note that the coverage relation between the rejection regions is an abstract relationship. Figure 2 shows the input of the dominance relations and the remaining steps into the Shiny web application.

Figure 1: (a) Decision Flowchart (b) Venn Diagram of Rejection Regions of Example 1

Step 2. Decompose the four hypotheses into subfamilies.

As shown in Figure 2, since both H_2 and H_3 are dominated by H_1 , so $I = \{2, 3\} \prec J = \{1\}$. According to the decomposition process in Li and Zhou (2021) and using the Shiny app `CoveringPrincipleMTP`, the whole family of three null hypotheses $\{H_1, H_2, H_3\}$ are decomposed into two subfamilies: $\{H_1\}, \{H_2, H_3\}$, corresponding to the maximum unconstrained class $\mathcal{R} = \{\{1\}, \{2, 3\}\}$.

Step 3. Test the null hypotheses in each decomposed subfamily.

Figure 2: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 1

Suppose that observed p -values for three hypotheses are: $p_1 = 0.04, p_2 = 0.026, p_3 = 0.003$ and the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, Holm's procedure is used for testing the two subfamilies for the sake of simplicity. Then, H_1 is rejected in its respective subfamily: $\{H_1\}$; similarly for H_2, H_3 in $\{H_2, H_3\}$.

Step 4. Consolidate the results from all of three subfamilies to make conclusions on an individual hypothesis.

(4a) The hypothesis H_1 on the primary endpoint is rejected because there is no constrain on H_1 .

(4b) The hypothesis H_2 on the secondary endpoint (S_1) can also been rejected because not only is it rejected in the subfamily: $\{H_2, H_3\}$, but also its dominant hypothesis H_1 on the primary endpoint has already been rejected in Step (4a).

(4c) Similarly, the hypothesis H_3 on the secondary endpoint S_2 is also rejected by the same reason in Step (4b).

In conclusion, all three null hypotheses H_1, H_2 , and H_3 are rejected.

3. A Shiny web application: CoveringPrincipleMTP

A Shiny web app named `CoveringPrincipleMTP` is developed in R, which implements the sieve decomposition method (Zhou and Li, 2023) and provides users with a graphical user interface (GUI) for building their own multiple testing procedure based on the Covering Principle.

Users can go to <https://hexaa.shinyapps.io/CoveringPrincipleMTP/> to launch the web app. Upload the dominance relations text file, enter the number of null hypotheses, a significance level, test p -values, and click the **Submit** button. The decomposed subfamilies or the maximum unconstrained class will be displayed on the screen. Figure 2 above shows the steps and test results for Example 1.

Note that users must define the dominance relations among the hypotheses and save it as a `.csv` file before using `CoveringPrincipleMTP`. A detailed walk through of the web app will be given by Example 2 in Section 4.1.

4. Applications of the Covering Principle in clinical trials

4.1. A clinical trial with superiority and non-inferiority assessments

Example 2: Dmitrienko and Tamhane (2007) applied a tree-structured gatekeeping procedure to a clinical trial, in which a new formulation A of an insulin therapy is compared to a standard formulation B on an endpoint: Hemoglobin A1c from baseline to a 6-month in Type II diabetes patients. Patients were allocated to three treatment groups: A vs B , $A + B$ vs B , and $A + B$ vs A with both a non-inferiority and a superiority assessments for each treatment group. Thus, there is a combination of six null hypotheses in total as shown in Table 1. The primary objective of the study is the non-inferiority test in the treatment group A vs B . If it is significant, a superiority test in this treatment group will be tested, and a non-inferiority test in the second treatment group $A + B$ vs B will be carried out. If these are also significant, a superiority test will continue in the same group, and a non-inferiority test will be carried out in the third treatment group $A + B$ vs A . If these are also significant, a superiority test will continue in the third treatment group. Dmitrienko and Tamhane (2007) developed a tree-based test strategy as shown in Figure 3.

Table 1: Null hypotheses, their hierarchical tree-structure and observed p -values in Example 2

Tier	Null Hypothesis	Treatment	Observed p -value
1	H_1 (Non-inf)	A vs B (Noninferiority test) A: New formulation; B: Standard formulation	0.011
2	H_2 (Super)	A vs B (Superiority test)	0.023
2	H_3 (Non-inf)	A+B vs B (Noninferiority test)	0.006
3	H_4 (Super)	A+B vs B (Superiority test)	0.018
3	H_5 (Non-inf)	A+B vs A (Noninferiority test)	0.042
4	H_6 (Super)	A+B vs A (Superiority test)	0.088

The Covering Principle is used to construct a multiple testing procedure as follows.

Step 1. The development of the dominance relations among null hypotheses is associated with each particular study. According to the test strategy as shown in Figure 3 below, we have three dominance relations: $\{2, 3\} \prec 1$, $\{4, 5\} \prec 3$, $6 \prec 5$, which are listed in Table 2 as well as its text file named by `DmitTamh07.csv`,

Figure 3: Testing strategy of Example 2

Table 2: Dominance relation, `DmitTamh07.csv`, and decompose subsets in Example 2

No k	Dominance Relations $\{I_k\} \prec \{J_k\}$	<code>DmitTamh07.csv</code> text file contents	Maximum Remainder Class (Decomposed Subsets)
1	$\{2, 3\} \prec \{1\}$	2,3	$\{2, 4, 5\}$
2	$\{4, 5\} \prec \{3\}$	1	$\{2, 4, 6\}$
3	$\{6\} \prec \{5\}$	4,5	$\{2, 3\}$
4		3	$\{1\}$
5		6	
6		5	

in which each dominance relation is entered in a pair of two consecutive lines with the first line being I_k and the second line J_k ; a comma is used as the separator between indices if needed. No header line is entered in the text file. Table 2 shows the contents of `DmitTamh07.csv`.

Step 2. Go to <https://hexaa.shinyapps.io/CoveringPrincipleMTP/> to launch the web app and a GUI will be shown as in Figure 4. Upload the dominance relation text file by clicking **Browse** and selecting `DmitTamh07.csv` in your smart device or a computer. Note the default separator in the `DmitTamh07.csv` is a **Comma**. You may select **Semicolon** or **Tab** accordingly if your text file uses them as a separator. Enter the number of null hypotheses 6, the significance level 0.05, the test p -values, and click the **Submit** button. The decomposed subfamilies will be displayed on the screen. If **Head** is selected in the **Display**, only the first six lines of the dominance relations and the first six decomposed subfamilies will be displayed on the screen. The default display is **All**.

When all decomposed subfamilies are displayed on the screen as shown in Figure 5, users can select which multiple testing procedure to apply for each subfamily. The default is the Holm procedure. In Example 2, the Holm procedure

The Covering Principle

Choose CSV File for Dominance Relations

Browse... InsulinDmi2007.bt

Upload complete

Separator

Comma

Semicolon

Tab

Display

Head

All

Number of Null Hypotheses

6

Enter value for ALPHA

0.05

Enter P-value: (separated by comma)

0.011,0.023,0.006,0.018,0.042,0.088

Submit

Home Instruction

Dominance Relations

V1	V2
2	3
1	NA
4	5
3	NA
6	NA
5	NA
2	NA
1	NA
3	NA
1	NA
4	NA
3	NA
5	NA
3	NA
4	NA
1	NA
5	NA
1	NA
6	NA
3	NA
6	NA
1	NA

Figure 4: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 2

is used for two subfamilies: $\{2, 3\}$, $\{1\}$, and the fixed sequence procedure is used for subfamilies $\{2, 4, 5\}$ and $\{2, 4, 6\}$. This results in the rejection of hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 while the hypothesis 6 is not rejected. However, the Bonferroni-based gatekeeping procedure only rejected hypotheses 1, 2, 3, and 4. Therefore, the efficacy on the endpoint of the treatment $A + B$ (the non-inferiority) could be claimed as a success compared to the treatment A . It is worth noting that Burman *et al.* (2009) rejected same five null hypotheses employing the graphical recycling method.

Shiny web app decomposed the whole family of null hypotheses into four unconstrained subfamilies as shown in Table 2.

Step 3. For comparison purposes, the same set of observed p -values in Dmitrienko *et al.* (2007): $p_1 = 0.011$, $p_2 = 0.023$, $p_3 = 0.006$, $p_4 = 0.018$, $p_5 = 0.042$, $p_6 = 0.088$ are used for the Covering Principle. The significance level was $\alpha = 0.05$ for the whole family of six null hypotheses.

In general, any α -level multiple testing procedure can be used for each sub-family using the Covering Principle, and this is reflected in the web app. The

Figure 5: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 2

correct procedures to apply for each sub-family depend on the case-by-case specifics. For illustrative purposes, two combinations of existing multiple testing procedures are used for respective subfamilies in Example 2, namely, “HmFix”, and “HmFb”.

“HmFix” is a combination of Holm and the fixed sequence procedures for subfamilies, in which some subfamilies are tested by Holm procedure and others by the fixed sequence procedure. Table 3 shows a fixed sequence procedure with specified testing orders used in subfamilies $\{2, 4, 5\}$ and $\{2, 4, 6\}$, and the Holm procedure is used in the subfamilies $\{2, 3\}$ and $\{1\}$. The reason why a fixed sequence procedure is applied to the first subfamily $\{2, 4, 5\}$ is that there is a natural testing order in this subfamily. H_2 being in the second tier would be tested before both H_4 and H_5 in the third tier. Since for each treatment group, a superiority test will be performed if a non-inferiority test is significant, then a non-inferiority test will be carried out in the second treatment group. Hence, the testing order is $2 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 5$. Users can click **Fixed** on the screen in Figure 5 to the right of the corresponding subfamily $\{2, 4, 5\}$, then click **Set Testing Order** and enter the order as shown in Figure 5. Based on the observed p -values, all three hypotheses H_2, H_4, H_5 are rejected by the fixed sequence procedure. Similarly, the testing order for subfamily $\{2, 4, 6\}$ is $2 \rightarrow 4 \rightarrow 6$, and both H_2 and H_4 are significant.

The reason why Holm’s procedure is used for the subfamily $\{2, 3\}$ is that the two hypotheses are from the same second tier in the hierarchical decision tree. Please note the testing strategy and specified testing order used in this example are just for illustration. Table 3 summarizes the testing procedures and results.

Step 4. Finally, the proposed combination of multiple testing procedures “HmFix” rejects five null hypotheses H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 , and H_5 , one more rejection of the null hypothesis (H_5) than the gate-keeping method.

The second combination of multiple testing procedures “HmFb” uses Holm’s procedure for subfamilies $\{2, 3\}$ and $\{1\}$ and the fallback procedure for subfamilies $\{2, 4, 5\}$ and $\{2, 4, 6\}$. For illustration purposes, the same testing order as the fixed sequence procedure is used in each subfamily by the fallback procedure. In addition, weights $w_1 = 0.85, w_2 = 0.1, w_3 = 0.05$ are assigned to the hypotheses H_2, H_4, H_5 , respectively. For the sake of simplicity, the same weight

Table 3: Two multiple testing procedures and results for Example 2

No	Subfamilies	HmFix	HmFb
1	{2, 4, 5}	$2^* \rightarrow 4^* \rightarrow 5^*$	$2^* \rightarrow 4^* \rightarrow 5^*$
2	{2, 4, 6}	$2^* \rightarrow 4^* \rightarrow 6$	$2^* \rightarrow 4^* \rightarrow 6$
3	{2, 3}	Holm {2*, 3*}	Holm {2*, 3*}
4	{1}	Holm {1*}	Holm {1*}
	Final Rejection:	H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5	H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5

1): Suppose observed two-sided p-values are: $p_1 = 0.011, p_2 = 0.023, p_3 = 0.006, p_4 = 0.018, p_5 = 0.042, p_6 = 0.088$. The asterisk * means the corresponding null hypothesis is rejected in that subfamily by its corresponding multiple testing procedure; The significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

2): “HmFix” is a combination of the Holm and the fixed sequence procedures used for the subset. “HmFb” is a combination of Holm and the fallback procedures used for the subset. In particular, either a fixed sequence or a fallback procedure was used in subsets {2, 4, 5} and {2, 4, 6}. Holm procedure was used in subset {2, 3} and {1}.

3): For the fallback procedure, a weight scheme $w_1 = 0.85, w_2 = 0.10, w_3 = 0.05$ are used in the subfamily {2, 4, 5} and {2, 4, 6}.

Figure 6: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 2

scheme is also used for the subfamily {2, 4, 6}. “HmFb” rejects the same five null hypotheses H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4 , and H_5 as “HmFix”. How to enter the testing order and their corresponding weights is shown in Figure 7.

In Example 2, users might see that the Covering Principle does not dictate which multiple testing procedure is used for which subfamily. The flexibility of the Covering Principle stems from the freedom of choice of any α -level test for each subfamily. The freedom of choice enhances the ability for users not only to construct an objective-tailored multiple testing procedure, but also to increase the power in practice.

4.2. A clinical trial with multiple endpoints and multiple doses

Example 3: Dmitrienko *et al.* (2007) discussed a dose-finding clinical trial for Type II diabetes patients, in which the effects of low (L), medium (M), and high (H) doses of an experimental drug were compared to a placebo on one

Figure 7: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 2

primary endpoint (P): Haemoglobin A1c, and two secondary endpoints: Fasting serum glucose (S1) and HDL cholesterol (S2). Therefore, there was a combination of nine null hypotheses as shown in Table 4, along with their corresponding p -values. The clinical trial sponsors developed a testing strategy where the primary endpoint is tested first within each dose level, and the secondary endpoint (S1) will be tested only if the primary endpoint is significant. Similarly, the secondary endpoint (S2) will be tested only if both the hypotheses on both the primary (P) and secondary (S1) have demonstrated significant results. Their testing strategy is shown in Figure 8.

The Covering Principle is used to construct multiple testing procedures in the following steps.

Table 4: Null hypotheses on multiple endpoints with multiple doses and their observed p -values in Example 3

Tier	Null Hypothesis	Endpoints	Observed p -value
1	H_1	High dose on Primary endpoint	0.005
1	H_2	Medium dose on Primary endpoint	0.011
1	H_3	Low dose on Primary endpoint	0.018
2	H_4	High dose on Secondary endpoint S1	0.009
2	H_5	Medium dose on Secondary endpoint S1	0.026
2	H_6	Low dose on Secondary endpoint S1	0.013
3	H_7	High dose on Secondary endpoint S2	0.010
3	H_8	Medium dose on Secondary endpoint S2	0.006
3	H_9	Low dose on Secondary endpoint S2	0.051

Step 1. According to the testing strategy in Figure 8, we can establish the following dominance relations: $\{7\} \prec \{4\} \prec \{1\}$, $\{8\} \prec \{5\} \prec \{2\}$, and

$\{9\} \prec \{6\} \prec \{3\}$. The first dominance relation can be separated as the following: $\{7\} \prec \{4\}$, $\{4\} \prec \{1\}$, $\{7\} \prec \{1\}$. Similarity, the second and third ones can also be separated as $\{8\} \prec \{5\}$, $\{5\} \prec \{2\}$, $\{8\} \prec \{2\}$, and $\{9\} \prec \{6\}$, $\{6\} \prec \{3\}$, $\{9\} \prec \{3\}$. These dominance relations are entered into the text file `Dmitrienko2007Dose.csv` and its contents are shown in Table 5.

Step 2. Go to <https://hexaa.shinyapps.io/CoveringPrincipleMTP/> to launch the web app and a GUI will be shown as in Figure 9. Upload the dominance relation text file `Dmitrienko2007Dose.csv`, enter the number of hypotheses 9 and their p -values, and the significance level 0.05, and then click **Submit**. Then, all decomposed subfamilies are displayed on the screen 10, and users can select which multiple testing procedure to apply for each subfamily. The default is the Holm’s procedure.

Figure 8: Testing strategy of Example 3

Step 3. For illustrative purposes, three combinations of existing multiple testing procedures are used for respective subfamilies in Example 3, namely, “HmFix”, “HmFb”, and “Hm”.

In Example 3, “HmFix” procedure is implemented in this way: a Holm procedure is used for each of three subfamilies: $\{1, 2, 3\}$, $\{4, 5, 6\}$, $\{7, 8, 9\}$, and the fixed sequence procedure is used for the rest 24 subfamilies. Table 6 and Figure 10 show a fixed sequence procedure with specified testing orders used in those 24 subfamilies.

The reason why the fixed sequence procedure is applied to the second subfamily $\{1, 2, 6\}$ is that there is a natural testing order in this subfamily. H_1 and H_2 being in the first tier, they would be tested before H_6 in the second tier. Although H_1 and H_2 are hypotheses on the same endpoint in the same tier, H_1 is the high dose and would, therefore, be tested before H_2 . Hence, the testing order is $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 6$. Based on the observed p -values, all three hypotheses H_1, H_2, H_6 are rejected by the fixed sequence procedure. Similarly, the testing order for other subfamilies can be established according to the testing strategy in Figure 8. Please note the specified testing order used in this example is for

Table 5: Dominance relation, `Dmitrienko2007Dose.csv` text file, and decomposed subsets in Example 3

No k	Dominance Relations $\{I_k\} \prec \{J_k\}$	<code>Dmitrienko2007Dose.csv</code> text file contents	Maximum Remainder Class (Decomposed Subsets)
1	$\{7\} \prec \{4\} \prec \{1\}$	7	$\{1, 2, 3\}$
2	$\{8\} \prec \{5\} \prec \{2\}$	4	$\{1, 2, 6\}$
3	$\{9\} \prec \{6\} \prec \{3\}$	4	$\{1, 2, 9\}$
4		1	$\{1, 3, 5\}$
5		7	$\{1, 3, 8\}$
6		1	$\{1, 5, 6\}$
7		8	$\{1, 5, 9\}$
8		5	$\{1, 6, 8\}$
9		5	$\{1, 8, 9\}$
10		2	$\{2, 3, 4\}$
11		8	$\{2, 3, 7\}$
12		2	$\{2, 4, 6\}$
13		9	$\{2, 4, 9\}$
14		6	$\{2, 6, 7\}$
15		6	$\{2, 7, 9\}$
16		3	$\{3, 4, 5\}$
17		9	$\{3, 4, 8\}$
18		3	$\{3, 5, 7\}$
19			$\{3, 7, 8\}$
20			$\{4, 5, 6\}$
21			$\{4, 5, 9\}$
22			$\{4, 6, 8\}$
23			$\{4, 8, 9\}$
24			$\{5, 6, 7\}$
25			$\{5, 7, 9\}$
26			$\{6, 7, 8\}$
27			$\{7, 8, 9\}$

The Covering Principle

Choose CSV File for Dominance Relations

Browse... DosefindingDem2007.txt

Upload complete

Separator

Comma

Semicolon

Tab

Display

Head

All

Number of Null Hypotheses

9

Enter value for ALPHA

0.05

Enter P-value: (separated by comma)

0.005,0.011,0.018,0.009,0.026,0.013,0.010,0.006,0.051

Submit

Home Instruction

Dominance Relations

V1
7
4
4
1
7
1
8
5
5
2
8
2
9
6
6
3
9
3

Figure 9: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 3

illustration purpose only.

Holm’s procedure is used for $\{1, 2, 3\}$ since three hypotheses are from the same tier. Table 6 shows the testing order and summarizes rejections of each individual hypothesis with an asterisk * in each subfamily.

Step 4a. Since both H_1, H_2 and H_3 are the dominant hypotheses and are rejected in all subfamilies which contain them, all of them are ultimately rejected.

Step 4b. In order for a dominated hypothesis such as H_4 to be rejected, it must be rejected in all subfamilies containing H_4 , and its dominant hypothesis H_1 must also be rejected. Since H_1 is already rejected in *Step 4a*, H_4 is ultimately rejected. Similarly, H_7 is also rejected because its dominant hypotheses H_1 and H_4 have been already rejected.

In summary, the “HmFix” procedure rejected eight null hypotheses $H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7$, and H_8 , and did not reject H_9 . However, the Bonferroni-based gatekeeping procedure only rejected four null hypotheses H_1, H_2, H_4, H_7 , and the re-sampling gatekeeping procedure rejected six null hypotheses $H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_6, H_7$. The Covering Principle rejected more hypotheses than both gatekeeping procedures (Dmitrienko *et al.*, 2007).

Another combination of multiple testing procedures “HmFb” is also used for this example. “HmFb” stands for a combination of Holm and the fallback procedures, which replaces the fixed sequence procedure in “HmFix”. Like a

Table 6: Three new multiple testing procedures and testing results for Example 3

No	Subfamilies	HmFix	HmFb	Hm
1	{1, 2, 3}	Holm{1*, 2*, 3*}	Holm{1*, 2*, 3*}	{1*, 2*, 3*}
2	{1, 2, 6}	1* → 2* → 6*	1* → 2* → 6*	{1*, 2*, 6*}
3	{1, 2, 9}	1* → 2* → 9	1* → 2* → 9	{1*, 2*, 9}
4	{1, 3, 5}	1* → 3* → 5*	1* → 3* → 5*	{1*, 3*, 5*}
5	{1, 3, 8}	1* → 3* → 8*	1* → 3* → 8*	{1*, 3*, 8*}
6	{1, 5, 6}	1* → 5* → 6*	1* → 5* → 6*	{1*, 5*, 6*}
7	{1, 5, 9}	1* → 5* → 9	1* → 5* → 9	{1*, 5, 9}
8	{1, 6, 8}	1* → 6* → 8*	1* → 6* → 8*	{1*, 6*, 8*}
9	{1, 8, 9}	1* → 8* → 9	1* → 8* → 9	{1*, 8*, 9}
10	{2, 3, 4}	2* → 3* → 4*	2* → 3* → 4*	{2*, 3*, 4*}
11	{2, 3, 7}	2* → 3* → 7*	2* → 3* → 7*	{2*, 3*, 7*}
12	{2, 4, 6}	2* → 4* → 6*	2* → 4* → 6*	{2*, 4*, 6*}
13	{2, 4, 9}	2* → 4* → 9	2* → 4* → 9	{2*, 4*, 9}
14	{2, 6, 7}	2* → 6* → 7*	2* → 6* → 7*	{2*, 6*, 7*}
15	{2, 7, 9}	2* → 7* → 9	2* → 7* → 9	{2*, 7*, 9}
16	{3, 4, 5}	3* → 4* → 5*	3* → 4* → 5*	{3*, 4*, 5*}
17	{3, 4, 8}	3* → 4* → 8*	3* → 4* → 8*	{3*, 4*, 8*}
18	{3, 5, 7}	3* → 5* → 7*	3* → 5* → 7*	{3*, 5*, 7*}
19	{3, 7, 8}	3* → 7* → 8*	3* → 7* → 8*	{3*, 7*, 8*}
20	{4, 5, 6}	Holm{4*, 5*, 6*}	Holm{4*, 5*, 6*}	{4*, 5*, 6*}
21	{4, 5, 9}	4* → 5* → 9	4* → 5* → 9	{4*, 5, 9}
22	{4, 6, 8}	4* → 6* → 8*	4* → 6* → 8*	{4*, 6*, 8*}
23	{4, 8, 9}	4* → 8* → 9	4* → 8* → 9	{4*, 8*, 9}
24	{5, 6, 7}	5* → 6* → 7*	5* → 6* → 7*	{5*, 6*, 7*}
25	{5, 7, 9}	5* → 7* → 9	5* → 7* → 9	{5, 7*, 9}
26	{6, 7, 8}	6* → 7* → 8*	6* → 7* → 8*	{6*, 7*, 8*}
27	{7, 8, 9}	Holm{7*, 8*, 9*}	Holm{7*, 8*, 9*}	{7*, 8*, 9}
	Final Rejection:	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7

1): Suppose observed two-sided p -values: $p_1 = 0.005, p_2 = 0.011, p_3 = 0.018, p_4 = 0.009, p_5 = 0.026, p_6 = 0.013, p_7 = 0.010, p_8 = 0.006, p_9 = 0.051$. The asterisk * means the corresponding null hypothesis is rejected in that subset by its corresponding multiple testing procedure; The significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

2): “Hm” means Holm procedure is used for each subfamily; “HmFix” is a combination of Holm and the fixed sequence procedures used for the subfamily. “HmFb” is a combination of Holm and the fallback procedures used for the subfamily. In particular, either a fixed sequence or a fallback procedure was used in subfamilies No.2 through No.10, No.21 through No. 26.. Holm procedure was used in subfamilies No.1, 20, 27. The “→” denotes the specified testing order in both the fixed and fallback procedures.

3): For the fallback procedure, a weight scheme $w_1 = 0.85, w_2 = 0.10, w_3 = 0.05$ is used for three hypotheses in each subfamily.

Figure 10: Graphical User Interface of Shiny web app of Example 3

fixed sequence procedure, a fallback procedure also follows a pre-specified order to test each hypothesis, but instead of using the whole α at each step as in the fixed sequence procedure, a weight is assigned to each hypothesis according to their clinical importance. For illustration, the same testing order as that in the fixed sequence procedure is used in a fallback procedure. Additionally, a weight scheme $w_1 = 0.85, w_2 = 0.10, w_3 = 0.05$ is used for three hypotheses in each subfamily in which a fallback procedure is used. For example, in the second subset $\{1, 2, 6\}$, the testing order is $1 \rightarrow 2 \rightarrow 6$, so H_1 is tested at a significance level $\alpha * w_1 = 0.05 * 0.85 = 0.0425$ and it is rejected because $p_1 = 0.005 < 0.0425$. Then, H_2 is tested at a significance level $0.0425 + \alpha * w_2 = 0.0425 + 0.1 * 0.05 = 0.0475$ and is also rejected because $p_2 = 0.011 < 0.0475$. Finally, H_6 is also rejected at the significance level $0.0475 + \alpha * w_3 = 0.05$ because $p_4 = 0.013 < 0.05$. Therefore, all three hypotheses in this subset are rejected.

In summary, “HmFb” rejects the same eight hypotheses $H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_5, H_6, H_7,$ and H_8 as “HmFix”.

The third combination of multiple testing procedures “Hm” is also used for comparison purposes. “Hm” means Holm procedure is used for each subfamily. For example, in the first subset $\{1, 2, 3\}$ in Table 6, Holm’s procedure begins testing H_1 with the smallest p -value and rejects it because $p_1 = 0.005 < \alpha/3 = 0.0167$; then, Holm tests H_2 with the second smallest p -value and rejects it because $p_2 = 0.011 < \alpha/2 = 0.025$. Finally, Holm’s procedure tests H_3 at the whole $\alpha = 0.05$ and rejects it. Therefore, all three hypotheses in the subset $\{1, 2, 3\}$ are rejected. After consolidation, “Hm” rejects the same six hypotheses $H_1, H_2, H_3, H_4, H_6,$ and H_7 as the re-sampling gate-keeping procedure and two

more null hypotheses than the Bonferroni-based gatekeeping procedure.

5. Closing remarks

The Covering Principle is applied to two real clinical trials and three combinations of multiple testing procedures are developed in Examples 2 and 3 using a new Shiny web application. The flexibility and power gains of the Covering Principle relative to the more common gatekeeping method is demonstrated. Using the Covering Principle and the Shiny web application, users can conveniently explore different test strategies with the clinical team and build an objective-tailored multiple test procedure.

The Covering Principle uses the dominance relations to describe the logical relationship among hypotheses in the modern clinical trials with hierarchical study objectives. The dominance relations are then used to decompose a family of hypotheses into subfamilies in order to construct a multiple testing procedure. Therefore, users should develop the dominance relation at the same time when the strategy is developed.

The Shiny web app `CoveringPrincipleMTP` implemented the sieve method (Zhou and Li, 2023) to decompose of a family of hypotheses into subfamilies. After decomposition, each subfamily is displayed on the screen so users can choose the appropriate α -level multiple testing procedure for each subfamily. Indeed, choosing different multiple testing procedures for various subfamilies may improve testing power as illustrated in Example 2 and 3. For example, the fact that there is the additional clinical information within subfamilies that can be used in hypothesis testing may point to the fixed sequence procedure as the right test for those subfamilies.

The Shiny web app `CoveringPrincipleMTP` developed in the article is available online, works with any devices, and gives the final rejections on each individual null hypothesis, which makes it more convenient for users to develop their own objective-oriented multiple testing procedure, without the burden of employing R or any specific statistical program.

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